

THE UNPREDICTABLE WAYS OF CLIMATE CHANGE, THE VIROCENE AND THE FUTURE OF TOURISM IN THE NEW NORMAL

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Abstract

The COVID-19 pandemic has generated an unparalleled crisis in the circles of tourism industries and beyond. The overcrowding of cities associated with the technological revolution applied to transport has contributed directly to the spreading of the virus worldwide. The tourism industry has been the primary victim and spreader of COVID-19. Though initially, the consequences of the pandemic remain obscured or, at best, uncertain, no less accurate seems to be that scholars have devoted their attention to describing the economic effects on the tourism industry. For some reason, the sociological effects are unexplored in the specialized literature, which is very hard to precise here. These consequences include geopolitical tensions, cultural hostility against strangers, or even the rise of new forms of consumption associated with virtual tourism and IA. This paper discusses the host-guest encounters while basing conclusions on netnography. Since the sample was not statistically represented, the obtained results cannot be extrapolated to other universes. Netnography has received some criticism in recent years, but it remains a fertile ground for understanding certain discrimination-related issues.

Keywords: Climate change; COVID-19; Virocene; Tourism industry; New Normal; Netnography.

AS MANEIRAS IMPREVISÍVEIS DA MUDANÇA CLIMÁTICA, O VIROCENO E O FUTURO DO TURISMO NO NOVO NORMAL

Resumo

A pandemia de COVID-19 gerou uma crise sem precedentes nos círculos das indústrias do turismo e além. As cidades superlotadas, associadas à revolução tecnológica aplicada ao transporte, contribuíram diretamente para disseminar o vírus em todo o mundo. A indústria do turismo tem sido a principal vítima e disseminadora da COVID-19. Embora as consequências da pandemia permaneçam obscuras ou, na melhor das hipóteses, incertas, parece não menos verdade que os estudiosos têm se dedicado a descrever os efeitos econômicos na indústria do turismo. Por algum motivo, que é muito difícil de precisar aqui, os efeitos sociológicos são inexplorados na literatura especializada. Essas consequências incluem tensões geopolíticas, hostilidade cultural contra estrangeiros ou até mesmo o surgimento de novas formas de consumo associadas ao turismo virtual e à IA. Este artigo se centra em discutir os encontros entre anfitrião e hóspede, baseando as conclusões em uma netnografia. Como a amostra não foi estatisticamente representativa, os resultados obtidos não podem ser extrapolados para outros universos. A netnografia recebeu algumas críticas nos últimos anos, mas continua sendo um terreno fértil para entender certas questões relacionadas à discriminação.

Palavras-chave: Mudança climática; COVID-19; Viroceno; Indústria do turismo; Novo Normal; Netnografia.

LOS CAMINOS IMPREDECIBLES DEL CAMBIO CLIMÁTICO, EL VIROCENO Y EL FUTURO DEL TURISMO EN LA NUEVA NORMALIDAD

Resumen

La pandemia de COVID-19 ha generado una crisis sin precedentes en los círculos de las industrias del turismo y más allá. Las ciudades superpobladas, asociadas a la revolución tecnológica aplicada al transporte, han contribuido directamente a la propagación del virus en todo el mundo. La industria del turismo ha sido la principal víctima y propagadora de COVID-19. Aunque las consecuencias de la pandemia permanecen oscuras o, en el mejor de los casos, inciertas, no parece menos cierto que los académicos se han dedicado a describir los efectos económicos en la industria del turismo. Por alguna razón, que es muy difícil precisar aquí, los efectos sociológicos no se han explorado en la literatura especializada. Estas consecuencias incluyen tensiones geopolíticas, hostilidad cultural contra extranjeros o incluso el surgimiento de nuevas formas de consumo asociadas al turismo virtual y la IA. Este artículo se centra en discutir los encuentros entre anfitriones y huéspedes, basando las conclusiones en una netnografía. Dado que la muestra no fue estadísticamente representativa, los resultados obtenidos no se pueden extrapolar a otros universos. La netnografía ha recibido algunas críticas en los últimos años, pero sigue siendo un terreno fértil para comprender ciertos temas relacionados con la discriminación.

Palabras clave: Cambio climático; COVID-19; Viroceno; Industria del turismo; Nueva Normalidad; Netnografía.

HOW TO CITE: Korstanje, M., & Kumar Kulshreshtha, S. (2024). The Unpredictable Ways Of Climate Change, The Virocene And The Future Of Tourism In The New Normal. *Anais Brasileiros De Estudos Turísticos*, 14(1). Retrieved from: <https://periodicos.ufrb.br/index.php/abet/article/view/44998>
DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14226283>

1 INTRODUCTION

Not surprisingly, the turn of the twentieth century has brought unanticipated and global risks that placed the tourism industry in jeopardy. These risks included the radicalization of political violence, if not terrorism (Saha & Yap, 2014, Korstanje 2023), followed by the ecological crisis

and climate change (Pang, Mc Kercher & Prideaux, 2013), without mentioning the recent COVID-19 pandemic (Sigala 2020). Climate change is creating serious challenges for the industry, which today cannot be resolved by policymakers. One of the problems of climate change is the paradox it creates. At the same time, authorities, the net of experts, and lay citizens are worried about its effects, and these fears

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cannot be crystalized in specific-driven policies to reverse its effects.

In fact, climate change and the current unsustainable form of exploitation are generating undesired consequences for the tourism industry. Some voices have alerted on the risks of virocene, the creation and circulation of lethal viruses that affect life at least as we know it (Korstanje 2017; Korstanje & Skoll 2014; Tzanelli, 2021).

The tourism industry is the main victim and carrier of pandemics. Having said this, tourism security occupied a central place in the academic debate just after the 2000s (Seabra & Korstanje, 2023). The SARS-COV2, originally dubbed COVID-19, was supposedly reported by the last days of December 2019 in the Chinese city of Wuhan. In question of weeks, the virus has rapidly spread to other regions in Asia and Europe, jumping to the US later. The overcrowded cities, as well as the fast transport, means which today connect distant cities in hours, have directly contributed to the virus dissemination (Nepal 2020; Lu et al. 2022). As Baum & Hai put it, tourism was the main carrier and victim of COVID-19 globally (Baum & Hai 2020).

At a closer look, the economic effects on the service sectors and the tourism industry have been devastating and long-lasting. Governments took the lead in implementing some restrictive measures originally designed to stop the pandemic. These steps ranged from the border and airspace closure to strict lockdowns in free circulation, travel, and public spectacles (only to name a few). Underdeveloped economies or economies subject to tourism dependency experienced more major losses than developed ones (Rogerson & Baum, 2020).

Of course, the literature discussing the economic effects of the COVID-19 pandemic on tourism simply abounds (Bakar & Rosbi, 2020; Gosling, Scott & Hall, 2020; Higgins-Desbiolles, 2020), but less attention was paid to the sociological and psychological effects on tourist behavior (Korstanje & George 2022). The new normal witnessed how societies recovered but at a snail's pace. The new normal has some serious implications that changed leisure practices as never before. These changes encompassed geopolitical tensions, racist or chauvinist expressions (above all against Asian tourists), health passports or biological certificates, or simply the rise of new forms like vaccine tourism have come to stay (Mostafanezhad, Cheer & Sin, 2020). However, applied research in this direction is necessary.

To fill the gap, the present research is centered on a netnography applied to tourists on specific websites regarding customer review behavior for hotels and travel organizations in a post-COVID-19 context. Since the method is not statistically representative nor the sample, the obtained results -though promising- should not be extrapolated to other universes.

2 COVID-19 AND TOURISM: A SHORT COMPANION

As stated in the introduction, the COVID-19 pandemic has brought unparalleled disastrous consequences for the tourism industry as well as for hospitality and global trade. Scholars who preliminary theorized on this have divided into two groups. On one hand, some voices applauded the opportunity to restore sustainable practices that solve the

ecological crisis, giving a new opportunity for mankind (Higgins-Desbiolles, Bigby & Doening, 2022; Ratten 2023), while -on another- other studies alerted on the obstacles to studying tourism in a world without tourists (Liu et al 2022).

Quite aside from any discrepancy, the COVID-19 pandemic accelerated a deep economic crisis that whipped the Western capitalist societies in 2008 but now with uncertain consequences in the long run (Romagosa, 2020). In this respect, Sharma & Nicolau (2020) offer a set of assessments that allows a credible diagnosis of the real impacts of COVID-19 on the tourism industry.

Governments have assisted the sector at different levels and stages in which case, which include tax reductions, financial bailouts, or different programs to incentivize consumption during the lockdown. As the authors conclude, the sectors associated with hotels, travel agencies, airlines, and car rentals have been notably affected, but doubtless, the cruise industry is the most damaged one. This happens because business travel (which needs tour operators, hotels, airplanes, and car rentals) recovers quicker than leisure travel.

What is more important, the cruise industry seems to be essentially limited to a private space where contagion spreads easier and faster. The highly publicized ads on Diamond Princes, as well as the tragedy of thousands of tourists stranded on the cruises without authorization to land, is an example of the manifest fear of consumers buying these services. The evaluation of the impacts of the pandemic varies on the nation and level of economic maturation. In consonance with this, Pham et al. (2021) argue that policy responses are very specific according to country and health contexts.

Having said this, the industry will be gradually recovering after 2024 at the least. Among the economic consequences, the authors enumerate the job losses, the destruction of the tourism value chain, the reduction of national GDP, the decline of investment, depressed rates of return, as well as serious disruption in the economy of scale. Rogerson & Rogerson (2020a; 2020b) reported that developed nations have further opportunities for rapid recovery than underdeveloped countries. Besides, those rural areas that are dependent on tourism have fewer odds to be recovered than urban areas. National and health authorities should make mixed-balanced diagnoses that contemplate public health as well as the future of the economy in the long run.

This is particularly important because not all governments have the same capacity for answer or recovery timeframe; some sub-services sectors, unless assisted are slumped down into disastrous contexts. Some studies have reported social conflicts among stakeholders in the recovery facet or simply are subject to discrepancies in the methods used to forecast the recovery time (Fotiadis, Polyzos & Huan, 2021; Jin, Bao & Tang, 2022). S. S Yeh (2021) explores the figure of travel as the main important component of the industry.

Crisis and disaster management should coordinate efforts to understand travel behavior to forecast the real intricacies of the current crisis; above all, management should work actively to placate the post-crisis effects. The government-sponsored loans (or bailouts) are essential to

protect the industry but the communication process plays a major role in configuring more resilient destinations in the years to come. Also, the future research direction should be gone to the social impacts of the pandemic on travel behavior. This point will be addressed with accuracy in the next section.

3 SOCIOLOGICAL EFFECTS ON TRAVEL BEHAVIOR

Not surprisingly, the literature suggests the negative effects generated by COVID-19 will last for several months. As hotly debated in the earlier section, the consequences are evaluated by experts from an economic lens (Mann 2020). Little evidence or studies focus on the sociocultural effects of the pandemic in society and the tourism industry. Some works emphasized the multiplication of psychological syndromes or mental illnesses derived from prolonged periods of isolation or lockdown (Xiao 2020).

The rise of depression or even suicidal acts has been reported in several works (Lakhan, Agrawal & Sharma 2020). What is more important, there are manifest geopolitical tensions among states and between authorities and citizens who are not in agreement with the restrictive measures (Korstanje & George 2021). Social protests against unemployment or the lockdown have been reported in Europe and the US. At the same time, emerging national expression against strangers has been documented by experts as well (Korstanje & George 2021; Kock et al, 2020; Mostafanezhad, Cheer & Sin, 2020).

In the constellations of tourism research, these studies do not abound. Although there is little understanding of how the COVID-19 pandemic altered our travel behavior, some preliminary studies can be discussed. One of the negative effects associated with the suspension of the right to travel or tourism right was creating a state of anxiety and constant protest in social imagination (Baum & Hai 2020; Tremblay-Huet 2020).

Phillipe Wassler has illustrated very well a durable state of conflict between hosts and guests derived from some travel anxieties. Under some contexts, the anti-tourist sentiment has been potentiated by the pandemic. For this instance, Tremblay-Huet (2020) alerts that even if the crisis resulted from the pandemic has certainly changed not only travel behavior but how leisure practices appropriate from the territorial spaces, it is beneficial for host communities. Given the problem in these terms, the tourism right should be re-interpreted along with the local initiatives, hosts' identity and their preferences.

In the name of tourism, many destinations have been gradually degraded in the case that domestic or degrowth tourism will signify a great advancement for sustainable practices in the future. It is not difficult to resist the impression the figure of the tour, which was originally esteemed as an ambassador of economic prosperity, has been in the center-storm of critics during the pandemic. As Korstanje & George (2022) describe, unfortunately, the industry was not only affected by the COVID-19 pandemic but also the figure of the tourists received a notable demonization, considering most of them as potential carriers of a lethal virus.

The act of touring was penalized as a criminal act that was confronted directly by health authorities and public order.

From that moment onwards, tourists are considered undesired guests. Similar remarks are found in Mostafanezhad, Cheer & Sin (2020) who analyze the expression of hostility against Asian tourists in social media. Per these authors, there is an underlying anxiety (if not xenophobia) directed against Asian (Chinese) tourists who are blamed as "spreaders that are being part of the problem".

It seems not to be difficult to resist the impression that a type of aversion to strangers has plausibly led to new forms of domestic tourism (Luo & Lam, 2020; Hoque et al. 2020). The opposite is equally true, anxiety to travel because of the risk to be infected accelerated the rise of new domestic forms of consumption and touring (Sengel et al 2023; Kamata 2022).

In consonance with this, Gymothy, Braun & Zenker (2022) hold that the state of panic, which took place during the pandemic, was supported and disseminated by social media. As a result of this, laypersons developed an "assortative sociality," which means an out-group avoidance or, so to speak, ethnocentric discourses. These sentiments resulted from the higher levels of anxiety and fear ignited by the pandemic and the strict lockdowns.

The incipient ethnocentrism has invariably changed travel behavior and the derivative decision-making process. Domestic tourism, to some extent, can be explained by the change of new patterns oriented to avoid strangers or unknown situations. Unless duly regulated, these dispositions may very well usher in ethnocentric traits undermining the opportunities for destinations to accommodate foreign visitors.

As the previous argument was given, customer review behavior has suffered some changes in the new normal (Haryanto, 2020; Cakmak, Issac & Butler, 2023). Domestic tourism or proximity tourism is situated as a leading niche worldwide. Tourists preferred nearby areas instead of international off-the-beaten-track destinations (Jeon & Yang, 2021).

In parallel, some travel restrictions and health passports have been implemented as security measures oriented to make safer travels (Koh 2020; Wen, Wang & Kozak, 2021). Digital technology was re-employed to monitor potential sick passengers and vehicles of sanitization and control (Serrano & Kazda, 2020). Domestic destinations, anyway, requested extensive migratory requirements such as medical (PCR) tests, health passports or even vaccination certificates. In a few words, the new normal changed travel behavior and security and safety protocols in transport hubs, hotels and tourist destinations (Nagai & Kurahashi, 2020; Korstanje & George 2022).

Here two assumptions should be made. At first glimpse, travel patterns and leisure practices have mutated to more virtual forms which have been widely supported by artificial intelligence (AI) (Zhang et al 2022; Talwar et al 2022). Secondly, not only consumers enthusiastically embraced virtual tourism as a form of mental displacement during the lockdown, but also tour operators, air companies, and hotels adopted digital platforms to optimize their sales. Consumers held mobile phones in their pockets and other devices while accessing vital information to improve their decision-making process (Chakravarty, Chand & Singh, 2021). At the same time, the internet has played a leading

role in assisting consumers to consult the best tourist information for their travels. In the pre-pandemic days, word-of-mouth (WOM) was the most relied source for information. In the new normal, this tendency triplicated and e-wom represented a driver towards more efficient forms of information and travel organization globally (Toubes, Araujo-Vila & Fraiz-Brea, 2021).

4 NETNOGRAPHY AS THE SCIENTIFIC METHOD

The term netnography was originally coined by Robert Kozinets to denote a qualitative method –derived from ethnography– using social media research. The recent technological breakthrough in the field of digital communications called for ethnography to work as a new method associated to data collection, research guidelines and ethics, as well as analysis and active participation engulfed into participant observation. Netnography is a combination of words such as internet + network.

Unlike classic ethnography, it is important to add that ethnography mainly emphasizes reflections or data exposed in online communities. In so doing, netnography does not need fieldworkers in the site (Kozinets 2002; 2012). In the time, this method has received supporters and detractors but it was mainly applied in the constellations of tourism research.

As Langer & Beckman eloquently note, one of the ethical dilemmas revolving around netnography seems to be the lack of consent of some users to take part of the research (Langer & Beckman, 2005). What is more important to discuss, exegetes of netnography hold that it is less time-consuming and less intrusive as a method (Kozinets 2002).

5 A FRESH CASE STUDY

The present study case is based on the commentaries posted by consumers in TripAdvisor in the post-COVID-19 context. Since the sample is not statistically representative, the obtained outcomes cannot be extrapolated to other universes or cases.

TripAdvisor is a global platform that offers hotels, air tickets, and tours to a wide range of audiences or net of consumers. Its section Travel Review (travel stories) is a helpful instrument to thousands of tourists who need advice on a certain tourist destination. We have selected three different cities: Buenos Aires, Rio de Janeiro and Madrid. The selection criteria were based on the profile of visitors to these cities is similar and they represent a similar-centered niche.

TripAdvisor is an American company that operates with hotels, air-companies and travel agencies globally. Founded by Stephen Kaufer, this group inspired millions of consumers to compare and buy cheaper rates while the travel reviews give some snapshot on the targeted destination. This review system has been subject to great controversy in recent years due to “false” reviews or unsubstantiated anonymous reviews posted to discredit certain destinations or companies. Fake reviews can potentially threaten a destination or a product if the necessary forms of controls are not duly implemented.

In each case, cities are pretty different or at least in large writ, so reviews vary considerably. For example, in the case of Buenos Aires, Sandy76 said:

“When we arrived in Buenos Aires it was extremely hot, so we decided to take the bus to get a feel for the city and determine which sites we wanted to view first. Our cruise ship was here for 3 days but we only had 1-1/2 days since we booked an all-day tour to Iguazu Falls. The city is huge and spread out, so you really need to plan the sites based on the bus stops. I recommend going to the first 2 sites on your list. Have lunch in the area and then continue riding to the next stop on your list”.

At the same time, Robert12 wrote:

“I loved Buenos Aires city I visited several Latin American cities and nothing is comparable to Buenos Aires city, even is larger than Madrid or Rio de Janeiro. At time, I flew from London to Buenos Aires directly and all Argentinians are great lovely persons”.

About Puerto Madero neighborhood, Mr. Smith claimed:

“Puerto Madero is the best part of Buenos Aires, it’s clean, spacious and beautiful. You can find a natural reserve which has walking, cycling trails which transport you into a quiet natural retreat within a bustling city”. Of course, Puerto Madero is a new neighborhood offered for dwellers of high-power purchase. Regarding tourism security, Max22 writes “Buenos Aires city is splendid and very secure. Its streets are replete of police and guards and Argentinian are very nice with foreigners. Of course, avoid to speak or make a joke on Malvinas-Falklands. Unlike Rio, we travelled and walked through the streets of this city at the nights”.

Rom19 had the opportunity to visit the three cities earlier and later the COVID-19 pandemic. She said that cities have changed a lot because of COVID-19.

“I worked over years as tour operator in Madrid, Spain. I love traveling abroad and meeting with new cultures and landscapes. During the pandemic I suffered crisis of anxiety because my job was in jeopardy. Once the lockdown was released, I made the decision to fly Buenos Aires and Rio where I have good friends. Things changed a lot after the pandemic, if you ask me. Buenos Aires witnessed an unparalleled crisis while Rio de Janeiro a political turmoil just former President Bolsonaro leaves the presidency. Anyway, Buenos Aires had some bad areas (known as villas de emergencia) which you should avoid. The pandemic associated to the current economic tumdown has accelerated a socio-economic crisis in the country”.

Some testimonies have alerted on the anti-British sentiment resulted from the Malvinas-Falklands War, as well as the chauvinist expressions during the final World Cup match between Argentina and France. Stelladora laments

“being British in Buenos Aires during the FIFA world Cup was not a good idea, they shouted el que no salta es un ingles those who do not jump are British people to

denote a sentiment of hostility against Britons. This sentiment is based on the last war between both countries for Malvinas-Falkland's. Paradoxically this hostility is extended to all English native speakers including Americans, Canadians or New Zealanders but not to those cultures occupied by the British Empire, for example la India or Bangladesh. As an ethnicity the Anglo-Saxons are put as enemies of the Spanish culture for Buenos Aires dwellers. I do not know if the same replies in other parts of the country. The Spanish imprint situates as superior (purer) than Anglo-Saxons who are compared to pirates. I do believe this happens because of the complicity of British crowns with pirates in the colonial past".

At the same time, Madrid and Rio have suffered the economic crisis resulted from the lockdown and the restrictive measures over the COVID-19 pandemic. Alex27 who lives in Madrid posted

"the pandemic has taught two important things. Firstly, the tourism is very vulnerable to these types of crises. And secondly, the states of emergencies suspend given rights we all thought they were inalienable. The right to touring or traveling was suddenly suspended by the government leaving tourists and conational stranded abroad. The new normal is mainly moved by proximity tourism, though I must confess the tourism industry is gradually recovering in these years".

Maxim59 goes to similar conclusion in his post

"in the pandemic I experienced a great fear. The implementations of lockdowns surprised me visiting Rio de Janeiro, I was sleeping three nights at the airport without assistance or food. This was a complete chaos and decontrol; we have not received assistance from the Embassy nor any national authority. People like me stayed at airport for days till I have been repatriated by a flight of Aerolineas Argentinas. From that moment on, I opted not to travel long distances, I make only proximity tourism, just in case, nobody knows when a new pandemic will knock on our doors".

Maria56 recognizes that

"Rio de Janeiro is beauty but not the best destination to travel. At least, foreigner tourists are often targeted of robbing and often the city shows the higher levels of crime in Brazil, similarly to some cities in South Africa. The best places of Rio are situated at the south, in tourist friendly beaches like Copacabana or Ipanema who are safer during the day".

Albert21 writes

"Rio is not the city people often believe, criminality and violence coexist but they are in a specific region of the city. What anyone can do is to avoid "the problematic areas" or not to accept or do not trust in anyone who can offer a free ride from Airport to the hotel. Criminality was certainly reduced over the recent years but still remains higher in comparison with other destinations as Buenos Aires or Montevideo".

The question of xenophobia or chauvinist expression for Chinese (Asian) tourists is of vital importance to

understand the changes in consumers after the pandemic. By the way, lay-people see in Asian tourists the potential spreaders or carriers of a lethal virus. Originally reported in Wuhan, China, this country is targeted as the cradle of the COVID-19. Because of international travels and tourism as well as by the overcrowds in cities have spread the virus in questions of months. Some studies have alerted on the rise of chauvinist expression or hostility against Asian tourists globally. Chrales11 posted his opinion saying

"I am Japanese and experienced great levels of mistreatments in the New Normal. Front desk staff treated me differently or I felt that also; what is important, I have heard opinion like the Virus was an invention of Chinese or something alike. As an invention, this suggests that China fabricated and infected the world causing thousand and millions of victims. Donald Trump echoed the thing of Chinese virus to blame Asian tourists, what do you think? Ignorant people will say yes this is a problem of Chinese tourists".

Similarly Rebecca12 made public her discontent how she was treated in Brazil in 2021.

"Asian tourists like me suffer daily discrimination in hotels and their travels as never before because of COVID-19. These acts range from verbal abuse to explicit discrimination. Many travel writers have alerted on this increasing problem. I believed this would disappear once the new normal but I was mistaken. This racism has been potentiated in the recent months. Many Asian are native from other countries like the US or Spain while speaking a perfect English or Spanish but they are discriminated as well. In some cases, I know of persons whose reservations have been unilaterally cancelled because they were Asian tourists. I am very sad incident like these happen even today. Asian tourists are targeted because of fear and ignorance, a tragic combination. The opposite is equally true, since the fear leads persons to discriminate Chinese visitors, the same happen in China respecting Western tourists who are seen with mistrust".

Mary-ann72 confessed she returned to China, after years of living in San Francisco, and she was put in quarantine over more than one month.

"The coronavirus challenged the lives of persons but altered serious geopolitical tensions among states. Tourists suffer part of this tension bearing and sharing a certain blame for the pandemic". In other cases, Asian tourists are blamed as "rule-brakers". Phillipland exclaimed "I am not a racist but I have been treated very bad by Chinese front desk workers in my stay in China. In some instances, they refused to speak me in English. One boy told me here we speak Chinese, English is spoken in the UK and US. what do you feel on that? I feel this is a result of the racism Chinese have experienced in the US regarding the COVID19, this is for sure a blowback" In a similar line of inquiry, Ciro22 writes "I remind a curious case in Buenos Aires, days after the first lockdown was imposed by President Alberto Fernandez. This was a sad moment where thousand of Argentinian stranded abroad without assistance or workers lost their jobs. In the mid of this mayhem, a group of Korean tourists not only violated the quarantine they were assigned to make at a specific hotel, but also wandered by the streets of Buenos

Aires city. This is a clear sign on the lack of engagement in Asian minds for Western culture”.

Last but not least, the pandemic has prompted radical shifts in travel behavior but what is more relevant, it created a symbolic chasm between Western and Eastern cultures. This point is coincidental with other studies such as Korstanje & George 2022; Mostafanezhad, M., Cheer, J. M., & Sin, H. L. 2020 or Wassler 2023.

6 CONCLUSION

The COVID-19 pandemic has generated an unparalleled crisis in the circles of tourism industries and beyond. The overcrowding of cities associated with the technological revolution applied to transport has contributed directly to the dissemination of the virus worldwide.

The tourism industry has been the main victim and spreader of COVID-19. Though originally the consequences of the pandemic remain obscured or at the best uncertain no less true seems to be that scholars have devoted their attention to describe the economic effects in the tourism industry. For some reason, which is very hard to precise here, the sociological effects are unexplored in the specialized literature. These consequences include geopolitical tensions, cultural hostility against strangers, or even the rise of new forms of consumption associated with virtual tourism and IA.

This paper discussed the host-guest encounters while basing conclusions on netnography. Since the sample was not statistically represented, the obtained results cannot be extrapolated to other universes. Netnography has received some criticism in recent years, but it remains a fertile ground for understanding certain discrimination-related issues.

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Term	Definition	Author 1	A2
Conceptualization	Ideas; formulation or evolution of overarching research goals and aims	x	x
Methodology	Development or design of methodology; creation of models	x	x
Software	Programming, software development; designing computer programs; implementation of the computer code and supporting algorithms; testing of existing code components		
Validation	Verification, whether as a part of the activity or separate, of the overall replication/ reproducibility of results/experiments and other research outputs		
Formal analysis	Application of statistical, mathematical, computational, or other formal techniques to analyze or synthesize study data	x	x
Investigation	Conducting a research and investigation process, specifically performing the experiments, or data/evidence collection	x	x
Resources	Provision of study materials, reagents, materials, patients, laboratory samples, animals, instrumentation, computing resources, or other analysis tools		
Data Curation	Management activities to annotate (produce metadata), scrub data and maintain research data (including software code, where it is necessary for interpreting the data itself) for initial use and later reuse	x	x
Writing - Original Draft	Preparation, creation and/or presentation of the published work, specifically writing the initial draft (including substantive translation)	x	x
Writing - Review & Editing	Preparation, creation and/or presentation of the published work by those from the original research group, specifically critical review, commentary or revision – including pre-or post-publication stages	x	x
Visualization	Preparation, creation and/or presentation of the published work, specifically visualization/ data presentation	x	x
Supervision	Oversight and leadership responsibility for the research activity planning and execution, including mentorship external to the core team		
Project administration	Management and coordination responsibility for the research activity planning and execution	x	x
Funding acquisition	Acquisition of the financial support for the project leading to this publication		

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Processo Editorial / Editorial Process / Proceso Editorial
 Editor Chefe / Editor-in-chief / Editor Jefe: PhD Thiago D. Pimentel (UFJF).

Recebido / Received / Recibido: 20.06.2021; Revisado / Revised / Revisado: 27.06.2024 – 28.08.2024 – 13.11.2024; Aprovado / Approved / Aprobado: 23.12.2024; Publicado / Published / Publicado: 30.12.2024.

Documento revisado às cegas por pares / Double-blind peer review paper / Documento revisado por pares ciegos.